

6. Pelikan W, Unger G. The activity of potentized substances. *Br Hom J* 1971;60:233-266.
7. Jones RL, Jenkins MD. Plant responses to homœopathic remedies. *Br Hom J* 1981;70:120-8.
8. Boyd WE. Biochemical and biological evidence of the activity of high potencies. *Br Hom J* 1954;44:6-44.
9. Mansvelt JD, Amons F. Inquiry into the limits of biological effects of chemical compounds in tissue culture, I. Low dose effects of mercuric chloride. *Z Naturforsch* 1975;30c:643-9.
10. Boiron J, Marin M. Action d'une 15e CH de sulfate de cuivre sur la culture de *Chlorella vulgaris*. *Assises scientifique homœopathiques* 1970;9:25-32.
11. Moss VA, Roberts JA, Simpson HKL. The effect of copper sulphate on the growth of the alga *Chlorella*. *Br Hom J* 1977;66:169-177.

Homœopathy and allergy

MOLLIE HUNTON, MB, BS, D(OBST)RCOG, MFHOM

Before discussing the clinical aspects of allergy, it is important to define modern terminology, and to have some understanding of the pathological changes that take place in an allergic situation. Allergy is defined as an altered, abnormal sensitivity to a specific substance (the allergen). Some further definitions are also necessary to more clearly understand the allergic situation.

Atopy. The state of altered immunity found in some individuals where allergic disease may occur following sensitization to allergens.

Food allergy. A form of food intolerance with evidence of abnormal immunological reaction.

Food intolerance. Reproducible, adverse reaction to specific food which is not psychologically based. It occurs even when the food is given "blind".

Food aversion. Psychological avoidance and psychological intolerance. An unpleasant reaction caused by emotions associated with the food. It does not occur when the food is given "blind".

Mechanisms of allergy

The immune system exists to distinguish self from non-self, harmless from harmful, i.e. food and drink, viruses, parasitic worms, etc.

There are various types of immune reactions, and a short explanation is helpful in understanding.

Immune reactions

TYPE I Immediate hypersensitivity

TYPE II Cytotoxic

TYPE III Antigen-antibody complex

TYPE IV Delayed cell-mediated hypersensitivity

Lymphocytes increase $\xrightarrow{\text{days}}$ contact dermatitis

Other responses also occur.

Digestion—IgA is released on the surface of the intestinal mucosa.

Atopic people may have a deficiency or incompetence of this mechanism.

Chemicals or heavy metals bound to protein.

Primary irritants—for example, bee sting, nettle rash, coal tar all are skin irritants.

Inhalation of smoke causes hypersecretion and bronchospasm.

Mechanisms of allergy

- (a) lack of enzymes, e.g. alactasia, which is a deficiency of lactase which causes cows' milk intolerance.
- (b) a pharmacological effect, e.g. caffeine in coffee
- (c) a histamine release, e.g. shellfish and strawberries
- (d) an irritant effect directly on the mucous membrane of the bowel or mouth
- (e) an indirect (toxic) effect caused by the effects of fermentation of unabsorbed food residues in the lower bowel.

How does it show itself?

Major allergic diseases are hay fever, rhinitis, asthma, conjunctivitis, dermatitis, urticaria, angioneurotic oedema and anaphylaxis.

In one recent survey 11% of school children were found to have asthma. A small number of people die each year from bee and wasp stings.

Drug allergy is an obvious manifestation, and migrainous headaches are also. Other conditions have a more tenuous link with allergy, e.g. rheumatoid arthritis, colitis, proctitis, malabsorption states and dermatitis herpetiformis (gluten sensitivity).

A further group are thought more often by the patients than by the doctors to be allergic in nature and have so far not been proven scientifically. They include infantile colic, insomnia, hyperactivity, psychosis and depression.

Other symptoms are claimed to have been reproduced in patients by testing them blind for their allergies. These symptoms occur in virtually every system, and often consist of syndromes which are unique to one patient only.

The following is a list of allergic diseases and the allergen that commonly provokes them:

Hay fever—seasonal—mixed pollen, or specific individual pollens

Rhinitis—moulds, house dust, cows' milk

Asthma—any inhaled allergen—commonly house dust, animal dander and cows' milk

Urticaria—60% of patients respond to a diet that excludes artificial additives (esp. tartrazine-E102) and aspirin

Eczema/dermatitis—milk, beef, eggs, chicken

Colic, snuffles and vomiting in babies—cows' milk

Migraine—tyramine-containing foods, e.g. cheese and chocolate, also fish, milk and oranges

Recurrent ear infections—cows' milk, house dust, pet dander

Coeliac disease—gluten in wheat, rye, oats and barley

Diagnostic tests

Unfortunately, these all tend to be unreliable. Both false positives and false negatives are obtained, and testing on different days may produce different results. Only reproducible results are therefore reliable.

History

There is often a close link between the exposure to the allergen and the symptoms, e.g. dust and animal dander may produce immediate sneezing or wheezing.

Skin tests

(a) intradermal—these have the advantage of being easily performed in the surgery; however, positive tests are common and do not always mean the allergen is causing symptoms.

(b) patch tests—in which the offending substance is put under sellotape on the forearm or back and read at 24 and 48 hours.

A positive result is shown by itching and dermatitis.

Eosinophilia

(a) mucosal, e.g. in the sputum.

(b) haematological, usually the eosinophil count is above 10% to indicate allergy.

Total IgE

This is measured on a blood sample. If less than 15, it is normal; if between 15 and 170, allergy is neither proved nor disproved; if greater than 170, the patient is usually atopic with more than one allergy.

RAST (Radio-allergo sorbent test)

This test is based on the fact that serum IgE rises to a peak one month after challenge with the allergen, then gradually drops off over six/twelve months unless a further challenge occurs. RAST shows a count from 0–4 for the specific IgE that binds to an allergen. A laboratory will perform a set series of tests including house dust, grass pollen, cat, dog, etc. The test is also available to foods at reference laboratories such as Cardiff.

Blind testing for food allergy

(a) sub-lingual—dilute extracts of foods, chemicals, dusts, etc. are placed under the patient's tongue in a blind manner. The patient then develops symptoms and the allergen can be identified. The advantages are that the patient develops his symptoms immediately on contact, but the disadvantages are that it takes a long time to carry out all the tests, and it has not been satisfactorily proved to be reliable.

(b) Naso-gastric blind testing. A naso-gastric tube is passed, and the food extract is given to the patient again in a blind way. The patient will then reproduce his symptoms. This has the disadvantage that it has to be carried out in hospital, but is reliable if the patient reproduces his symptoms when he is tested with the allergen more than once.

Diets

The specific allergen is avoided from the diet for four weeks. It is then re-introduced, and reproducible reactions are obtained. It is important when using this method, and especially with small children, to make sure that adequate nutrition is preserved. Once the allergen is identified, it can be re-introduced, then only taken occasionally, maximum once every three days. It is also important to make sure that the imposition of a strict diet on a child is not a symptom of illness in the parent, i.e. Muenchhausen's disease by proxy.

Unorthodox methods

It is claimed by various practitioners that the following methods give good reproducible results. However, they are not generally accepted methods, because they have not been subjected to stringent testing.

Pulse test—it is claimed that a rise in pulse rate occurs after taking the food that the patient is intolerant to. However, the pulse rate can alter and respond to anaphylaxis, emotion, and other situations including caffeine intake.

Muscle strength test—it is claimed that a decrease in muscle strength takes place after ingestion of the allergen. Again, this is not reliably reproducible.

Intradermal injections—these have been quite often used by allergists, including Mackarness, but are said to be of unproven value. Some allergists claim that they can reproduce the symptoms at certain dilutions, and achieve a “turn-off” dilution when the patient’s symptoms are reversed.

Cytotoxic food tests—these are carried out by laboratories which advertise in magazines. They claim that the white cells of food allergic patients die and disintegrate in the presence of the food to which the patient is sensitive. In fact, these tests are completely unreproducible and results fluctuate from day to day.

Vega test—This is an electroacupuncture method of testing, using homœopathic preparations and substances to which the patient might be allergic to interrupt the circuit. It is presently being evaluated at the Centre for the Study of Alternative Therapies in Southampton.

The causes of allergy

Inhaled—airborne particles and also chemical vapours, e.g. perfume, flowers, etc.

Eaten—any food

Chemical contamination of food, e.g. E numbers on food labels.

Alteration of the micro-flora of the alimentary tract, especially with *Candida*. This condition is known as dysbiosis on the continent.

Inhaled allergies cause rhinitis, asthma and eczema. They are characterized by a seasonal incidence, e.g. pollens and moulds. Even house dust may be seasonal in that symptoms are worse in the autumn when the central heating is turned on. There is always exacerbation of the symptoms on contact, and the symptoms improve in hot dry climates. Inhaled chemical sensitivity causes headaches, nausea and fatigue on contact with volatile petro-chemicals, e.g. petrol, paint and perfumes. It is often an industrial disease.

Symptoms suggestive of food allergy

Persistent fatigue, only partly relieved by rest

Idiopathic oedema of the fingers or ankles which is often mild

Bouts of tachycardia, unrelated to exercise or specific anxiety

Bouts of sweating for no apparent reason

Abdominal distension for no apparent reason

Marked fluctuations in weight

Dysbiosis. Alteration of the microflora of the alimentary tract causes bloating after food, pruritus ani, recurrent cystourethritis with no evidence of bacterial infection, recurrent gastritis, sugar & alcohol craving. It may occur after multiple courses of antibiotics and any of the symptoms of the above may be worse after antibiotics. It can be diagnosed by use of the Vega machine.

Treatment

This consists of allergen avoidance and de-sensitization.

Allergen avoidance

Avoiding the inhaled allergens means keeping chemicals to a minimum in the house, removing animals from the environment, and removing house dust. Mould spores and pollen are far more difficult to avoid.

The major eaten allergen is cows’ milk, and it is always worth trying four weeks without any milk, cheese, butter, yoghurt, chocolate, cream or ice cream before looking for further allergens. After that the common allergens are wheat, food additives, eggs and nuts.

If multiple food allergens are suspected, it is worthwhile considering a total avoidance diet. The patient takes only bottled water for four days. There is often aggravation of symptoms during this time, but improvement starts after day 5 or 6. A basic diet of lamb, rabbit, pears, carrots, parsnips, turnips, swedes, courgettes, sunflower oil and bottled water is introduced. Meat, fish, fruit and vegetables may be introduced two items per day. These usually react within 12 hours of introduction. Wheat, corn, oats, rye and barley are introduced singly only every four days. It is obvious that a diary of food intake and symptoms must be kept. The advice of a dietician must be sought if it is thought that shortages of dietary factors will occur. In children it is probably important to avoid the allergen for up to six months and then re-introduce it. Spontaneous remission is common, especially in children, consequently the allergen may give no further trouble.

Desensitization

Standard allopathic desensitization is expensive, unreliable and may cause harmful side effects, including death from anaphylaxis. It may need to be repeated annually and may not give continuing benefit. There is certainly no reliable way of desensitizing to food allergens.

However, homœopathic desensitization is safe, easy to administer and causes very few side effects. The occasional aggravation of asthma may occur particularly with house dust desensitization. Its efficacy has yet to be proved. However, many potentized preparations are available for desensitization, including house dust, cat, dog, horse dander, Apis, Vespa, Lac bovinum (milk), mixed pollen, mixed grasses, MAP (*Mucor Aspergillus Penicillium*).

A patient with multiple allergies may well respond to *Medorrhinum* which I also find useful in babies with snuffles. A family history of atopy may be treated with *Sulph.*, *Psor.* or *Calc. carb.* The patient’s constitutional remedy will help to raise his resistance out of season.

A homœopathic doctor is in a special position with regard to allergies, because he asks the questions that allopathic doctors do not. For example:

What causes your symptoms or aggravates them?

How does the weather affect them?

Are you upset by any particular food?

Have you any cravings for any foods?

Are any foods difficult to digest?

Do you have wind or distension after meals?
 Do you have symptoms if you do not eat on time?
 Do you have a sense of well-being after eating?
 Are you sensitive to smells?

I would now like to suggest some remedies for various allergic conditions.

Hay fever (Kent page 326 coryza, annual, hay fever)

All-c., Arund., Euphr., Nat-m., Psor., Sabad.

Urticaria (Kent page 1321 eruptions, urticarial)

Apis, Ars., Calc., Dulc., Led., Nat-m., Rhus-t., Sulph., Urt-u.

Asthma (Kent page 764 respiration, asthmatic)

Ambr., Arg-n., Ars., Ars-i., Cupr., Ip., Kali-ars., Kali-c., Lob., Puls., Samb., Sil., Spong., Stram., Sulph.

Eczema (Kent page 1312 eruptions, eczema)

Ars., Ars-i., Bar-m., Calc., Calc-s., Cic., Graph., Hep., Meg., Petr., Psor., Rhus-t., Sulph.

Migraine (Kent page 132 pain, headache)

Bell., Bry., Calc., Gels., Glon., Iris., Nat-m., plus most of the polychrests.

I would now like to discuss some rubrics which would give particular information about allergies.

Worse for alcohol (Kent page 1344 Generalities)

Ars., Lach., Nux-v., Op., Sep., Sulph.

Worse in autumn (Kent page 1345; this might indicate mould sensitivity)

Lach., Rhus-t.

Clothing, loosening amel (Kent page 1348; this indicates distension)

Lach., Lyc., Nit-ac., Nux-v.

Coal gas (Kent page 1348)

Arn., Carb-v.

The rubric, fasting while, page 1361, may help people who have withdrawal symptoms from stopping food at the beginning of an elimination diet.

Cal., Croc., Iod., Lach., Plat., Plb., Ran-b., Sep., Staph., Tab.

Food intolerance is generally well covered in Kent. Starting at page 1362 there are quite a lot of rubrics, including the following:

Bread Bry., Puls. (wheat allergy)

Coffee Canth., Caus., Cham., Ign., Nux-v.

Eggs Ferrum-met

Shellfish Carbo-v., Lyc., Urt. Ur.

Milk Aeth., Calc., Calc-s., Chin., Con., Lac-deflor., Mag-m., Nit-ac., Sep., Sulph.

Pastry Carbo-v., Lyc., Puls., Sep., etc. (wheat allergy)

Pork Carbo-v., Cycl., Puls., Sep.

This rubric is also repeated under Stomach, page 476, and various food intolerances can be identified using some of the following rubrics:

Hunger Graph., Iod., Kali-c., Sil., Sulph.

Obesity Calc., Caps., Ferrum., Graph.

Wet weather Ars., Calc., Dulc., Nat-s, Nux-m, Puls. Rhod., Rhus-t.

Appetite capricious, increased, ravenous.

Aversion to beef, bread, butter, cheese, chocolate, coffee, eggs, fats, fish, flour, meat, milk, pork, potatoes.

Desires, page 483: alcohol, bread, butter, etc.

Any food which is strongly craved is often an indication of allergy in that the food that the person is allergic to is addictive, and cravings or withdrawal symptoms occur if a regular intake of that food does not take place.

Also indicative of food allergy may be the following rubrics:

Distension, page 487

Emptiness, page 487

Eructation, page 489

Fullness after eating, page 498

and any other symptom related to the stomach or digestion, particularly if rare or unusual, because these indicate a syndrome specific to that patient.

There are a great number of homœopathic remedies, particularly the polychrests, with strong rubrics which may indicate allergies. Some useful remedies might be the following:

Ars. nit. Strong desire for sweet food, salt and highly flavoured food. The patient is worse after eating and may have diarrhoea. It is often a useful remedy in peptic ulceration.

Ars. Alb. desires fat (may indicate a milk allergy). Sensitive to smells (may indicate an inhaled, chemical allergen)

Aurum met. Craves alcohol—feels better for it. Alcoholism may be a manifestation of food allergy. When treating alcoholics it may not only be useful to stop the alcohol intake, but also any other food containing cereal grains.

Calc. carb. Desire for eggs. Pica in children. Older children and people dislike meat, coffee and milk. Milk disagrees with them. They often have strange desires e.g. to eat raw potatoes.

Carbo veg. Flatulence. Often prefers indigestible food!

Ferrum met. Aversion to meat, eggs and sour fruit.

Ignatia Capricious appetite (also *Bry.*, *China*, *Cina*). This could indicate bulimia nervosa with ravenous hunger and gorging of food, which would usually be followed by a gain in weight if the patient did not make herself vomit.

Lachesis Flatulence with intolerance of tight clothing.

Lycopodium Flatulence, distension, hungry, yet full up after a few mouthfuls. Desires sweet food. Aversion to meat and coffee. Upset by oysters.

Medorrhinum A remedy for people with multiple allergies, especially catarrh and asthma. Desires salt, sweet food, sour, pickles and iced, i.e. cold things.

Natrum mur. Ravenous hunger at 11 a.m.

Natrum sulph. Cannot digest starch, milk or potatoes.

<i>Nux vom.</i>	Desires tasty food, fat, rich food which upsets. May flush and can faint while eating, particularly with meat. There is often nausea, distension and indigestion two to three hours after food. Irregularity of the bowels, either constipation or diarrhoea.
<i>Phosphorus</i>	Craves ice cold drinks and ice cream. Desires salt, tasty food and spicy food. May have chronic loose stools (colitis).
<i>Plumbum</i>	Constipation with colic > firm pressure (colo).
<i>Psorinum</i>	The patient feels unusually well just before an attack e.g. of diarrhoea, asthma or eczema. Also used for sickly babies that fret, worry and scream at night, which can be a symptom of cows' milk intolerance.
<i>Pulsatilla</i>	Thirstless. Slow to digest, bloating and distension. Changeable stools.
<i>Sepia</i>	Nausea at the smell of food. Aversion to fat, meat and milk.
<i>Silica</i>	Milk upsets, constipation. Hot food and drinks produce sweats.
<i>Sulphur</i>	Desires sweet, fat, butter. Empty feeling about 11 a.m. Hungry, but poor appetite on sitting down. Thirsty +++. Flatulent distension. Early morning diarrhoea which drives him out of bed.
<i>Syphilinum</i>	Craves alcohol (Remedies to treat the effects of alcohol) Cerebral excitement - <i>Agaricus</i> Gastritis - <i>Crotalis Horridus</i> Worn out constitution - <i>Eupatorium</i> Mania - <i>Hyoscyamus</i> Jaundice - <i>Rumex</i>
<i>Thuja</i>	A remedy to antidote excessive tea drinking.
<i>Zincum</i>	Aggravation from wine.

REFERENCES

- 1 *Journal of the Royal College of Physicians* 1984; 18 No. 2.
- 2 *Mims Magazine* 1 October 1984.
- 3 Spear F. *Food Allergy*.
- 4 Mandell M. *5-day Allergy relief system*, Arrow.
- 5 Workman, Hunter & Jones. *The Allergy Diet*, Dunitz.